

reduces stress and aids focus. Taking regular breaks enhances concentration, while curiosity and asking questions encourage continuous learning. Collaborating with peers through teamwork promotes problem-solving, and believing in one's abilities fosters confidence and perseverance.

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TEACHING COMPENSATORY COMPETENCE THROUGH STORY TELLING IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Abstract. This article knowledge of foreign languages in the modern world is necessary, as intercultural contacts are expanding, international economic and educational integration is taking place, mobility and the prevalence of scientific and technical knowledge are increasing. Improving the quality of knowledge of foreign languages is necessary both from the point of view of compliance with the

standards of the third generation, and it is also necessary to increase the level of formation of students' communicative competences.

Keywords. *Communicative competence, compensatory competence, communicative-compensatory competence, facilitation, interaction, horizontal-facilitative interaction.*

Introduction. The purpose of teaching a foreign language to modern schoolchildren is not just to master the skills of foreign language communication, but also to form a communicative competence, the structure of which includes compensatory skills and abilities that make it possible to find a way out of the current difficult situation in the process of foreign language communication. To put it another way, the development of compensatory skills in schoolchildren is to instill in them skills that will help, if necessary, compensate for the lack of knowledge of a foreign language in foreign language communication. Therefore, it seems advisable to study the features of its formation and diagnosis at different stages of training. The following outstanding scientists were engaged in the development of the problem of the formation of compensatory skills and the use of authentic texts: K.S. Krichevskaya, G.I. Voronina, E.V. Nosovich, O.P. Milrud, etc.

Main part. The goal was achieved using such methods of scientific and pedagogical research as analysis of thematic literature, comparative and systematic analysis, expert survey, questionnaires, conducting experiments, and the author's own observations. In order to diagnose the level of formation of communicative and compensatory competence of students within the framework of horizontal-facilitative interaction, we used the following methods: the method of diagnosing the interactive orientation of the personality of N.E. Shchurkova, "Difficulties in communication with peers and adults" by A.G. Samokhvalova, a test for assessing the level of sociability and communication skills of V.F. Ryakhovsky. Due to the fact that the process of forming the communicative and compensatory competence of primary school students, as follows from the above analysis, is positively influenced by the horizontal-facilitated interaction of the teacher and students, let

us turn to the consideration of the latter concept and present the results of our experiment as a reasoned proof of our hypothesis. Such modern teachers as I.N. Avdeeva, E.L. Erokhina, V.E. Sumina, T.A. Fil and others addressed the issues of facilitated interaction in the educational process.

However, K. Rogers was one of the first to address this phenomenon, who proposed to interpret the term "facilitation" as stimulating, initiating, and exerting a positive influence on a person through a special style of interaction. We see the essence of horizontal-facilitated interaction within the framework of the formation of communicative and compensatory competence in the implementation of the subject-subject relationship between the teacher and the students. Currently, the appeal to the problem of facilitated interaction is due to a change in the status of the educational process as a whole. We are talking about the implementation of an educational service, where the teacher plays the role of a manager, escort and consultant in solving educational tasks. The essence of all changes in the status of a teacher is to increase his role as a communicator, to replace the frontal nature of the traditional educational approach with the pedagogical skill of the competence approach. Moving away from the so-called "directive pedagogy" implies abandoning the authoritarian regime teaching and the transition to an authoritative.

Conclusion. The implementation of communicative and compensatory competence, by which we mean the system of knowledge, skills, and personal qualities necessary for primary school students to overcome communicative difficulties through the integration of adequate strategic moves, which positively affects the productivity of interaction in the communication process, will contribute to its effective flow in an atmosphere of psychological comfort, without fear of overcoming certain difficulties and communicative barriers, overcoming sociocultural differences and communication difficulties. The presence of communicative and compensatory important personal qualities will allow a student already at the stage of primary school to be more socially competent, flexible and easier to adapt to any communication situation, to show communicative tolerance both in his native and in a foreign language. Summarizing the available theoretical

and practical developments in terms of the formation of communicative and compensatory competence of students, we came to the conclusion that it is the implementation of horizontal-facilitated interaction between the teacher and students will increase the efficiency of this process.

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THE SPEECH ERRORS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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